
ANALYSIS OF TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY OF SELECTED AGRICULTURAL LENDING SCHEMES IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA: AN APPLICATION OF STOCHASTIC FRONTIER APPROACH

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Abstract

The study analysed the technical efficiency of selected agricultural lending schemes in Rivers State, using stochastic frontier approach. The research questions were; are the agricultural lending schemes in Rivers State technically efficient? What are the factors that determine technical efficiency of the lending schemes? The study revealed that most of the loan beneficiaries of the lending schemes are males and that the Rivers State microfinance agency financed the highest number of beneficiaries in the study area within the years 2013 -2017. The study also revealed that majority of loan beneficiaries are educated, married and have large household size. The study further shows that majority of loan beneficiaries are small scale operators. Further findings show that all loan beneficiaries of the lending schemes were aware of the loan conditions before taking the loans and that the loan conditions are not stringent which implies that the lending schemes are accessible, On affordability, Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS), Rivers State Micro-finance Agency (RIMA) and Rivers State micro finance bank (MFB) are the most affordable lending schemes. The study findings further revealed that funds are available to be disbursed by the selected lending schemes to loan beneficiaries who complete their loan application process and are successful. An examination of technical efficiency of the selected agricultural lending schemes shows that the schemes are operating below the stochastic frontier potential output or best practice frontier potential or full efficiency. The study also revealed that River State Microfinance agency is the most technically efficient scheme. The key determinants of technical efficiency are number of employees, operating expenses, Assets, Age, Financial sustainability, Borrower per staff and loan intensity